

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	08	17	Banjul	N	13°26	39.125	W	16°34	31.432
End	2022	08	29	Dakar	N	14°40	28.079	W	17°25	48.667

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAING OBJECTIVES

The Tara Oceans Mission Microbiome Leg 17 took place between Banjul (Gambia) and Dakar (Senegal). It corresponded to the last AtlantECO “upwelling” leg, sampling the upwelling system off the coast of Gambia and Senegal. The two principal objectives of this leg were 1) to characterize the “pre-upwelling” marine microbiome state, and 2) to characterize the Oxygen Minimum zone (OMZ), off the coast of Gambia and Senegal. The samplings during this leg were established in collaboration with the IRD (Dr. Eric Machu) who are regularly sampling this area at specific stations. Considering the IRD cruise during the next upwelling season, which will take place in December 2022, we coordinated the samplings to capture the state of plankton ecosystems during the pre-upwelling season, in August 2022. The IRD will use the Tara Mission Microbiomes protocols for genomics in order to be able to compare the pre-upwelling and upwelling system states we sampled at the IRD regular stations (see below). This is of particular interest as upwelling systems are usually sampled during winter (upwelling season). Characterizing highly resolved plankton community structures through omics between summer and winter seasons will also us to better understand the transition mechanisms of the marine microbiomes in this large upwelling system. In addition, characterizing the OMZ in this system will allow us to evaluate its seasonal evolution and its impact on highly productive marine plankton communities sustaining the very productive fisheries in the zone.

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin Hertau
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Léo Boulon
3	CREW - Mecano	Loic Caudan
4	CREW - Deck	François Aurat
5	CREW - Deck	David Monmarché
6	CREW - Cook	Carole Pire
7	CREW - Media	Hugo Viel
8	GUEST - Artist	Giulia Grossman
9	GUEST - Observer	Amadou Diao
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Noé Poffa
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Pedro Junger
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Erica Becker
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Ange Bouramanding Diedhiou
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Samuel Chaffron
15	SCIENCE - F – additional	

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

Six stations are regularly sampled by IRD cruises off the coast of Gambia and Senegal (Fig.1).

During the Tara Mission Microbiomes, the first station (#0: 13.13N/17.00W), off the coast of Gambia, was sampled during leg 15 in surface (~15m).

The five next stations were sampled during leg 17, off the coast of Senegal. Stations #1,2,5 (#1: 13.87N/16.980W; #2: 13.87N/17.150W; #5: 14.58N/17.185W) were very coastal and surface-only samplings. At station #3 (13.87N/17.610W) the more extensive sampling occurred, targeting surface, deep-chlorophyll maximum (DCM), as well as OMZ. At station #4 (14.58N/17.680W) surface and DCM samplings occurred.

Figure 1. Location of sampling stations

The sampling strategy for surface and/or DCM stations was as follows:

- CTD profile (~600m)
- A20 SRF pump: omics + decknet
- Rosita SRF (48L): BGC, cDNA, HPLC, NP
- VMP (x2)
- WP2 horizontal 20 + 200um
- Rosita DCM (48L): Proteomics
- Rosita DCM (48L): BGC, eDNA, HPLC, Omics
- Manta (over lunch)
- Bow Pole
- WP2 vertical 20 + 200um (200m)
- Regent 680um (200m) x2
- Aerosols: 6h + 18h (linked to night watches)

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

The main objectives of leg 17 were achieved as we could sample all stations using the pump in surface and the rosette in the epipelagic layer. All stations could be sampled using the strategy as presented above.

In addition, we could perform a fine scale characterization of the DCM using a higher resolution sampling around the DCM (DCM-15m, DCM+15m) at both stations #3 and #4. At these stations we encountered a well-defined DCM around 45-50m.

We also succeeded in sampling the OMZ encountered at 95-100m at station #3. A relative OMZ was also identified at station #4 but around 60m, but was not sampled.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

(Provide an overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event)

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC – CAST – 0-1000	SML	SRF – PUMP	SRF – NET – WP11 20	SRF – NET – WP11 200	SRF – NET – Manta 330	EPI – CAST – 0-200	EPI – NET – WP11 20	EPI – NET – WP11 200	EPI – Régent 680	MESO – CAST – 0-1000	CAST – Trace Metals	VMP – Profile	TIA – Towed Array	BowPole	hTSRB
157	2022-08-19	N13°53.084	W016°57.617	1		1		1	1	1	1							2		1	
158	2022-08-20	N13°51.939	W017°09.110	1		1		1	1	1	1							2		1	
159	2022-08-22	N13°52.130	W017°36.41	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			2		1	
160	2022-08-25	N14°35.464	W017°39.760	1		1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1				2		1	
161	2022-08-28	N14°34.780	W017°11.160	1		1		1	1	1	1							2		1	

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

Protocol	Container type	TOTAL	157	158	159	160	161	AEROSOLS	UNDW BIO	CONTROLS	TOTAL
											0
DIC13	200-mL-bottle										0
DICTA	500-mL-bottle		1	1	3	3	0				8
DINO	60-mL-Bottle		2	2	10	10	2				26
HG-M	125-mL Bottle		0	1	5	5	1				12
MTE-BP	125-mL Bottle										0
MTE-F	125ml bottle, Double Zip-lock										0
NUT-2	20mLCryoV										0
MTE-T	125ml bottle, Double Zip-lock		1	1	1	1	1				5
HG-T	40mL bottle, Zip-lock										0
MB320	4-mL-Vial		2	2	6	6	2			1	19
MB023	4-mL-Vial		2	2	6	6	2			1	19
MB<02	50-mL-falcon		2	2	6	6	2			1	19
eDNA	sterivex		1	1	5	5	1			1	14
NP550	20-mL-vial		1	1	5	5	1			1	14
NP045	4-mL-Vial		1	1	5	5	1			1	14
HG	Zip-lock										0
PM	Zip-lock										0
S320	5-mL-cryotube		3	3	5	5	3			2	21
S023	5-mL-cryotube		3	3	5	5	3			2	21
S<02	5-mL-cryotube		3	3	5	5	3			2	21
P320	5-mL-cryotube		1	1	5	5	1			1	14
P023	5-mL-cryotube		1	1	5	5	1			1	14
DGAS	ExeV-12mL		2	3	15	15	3				38
DO18	AmberV-40mL										0
SAL	125-mL Bottle		0	1	5	5	1				12
NUT-1	20mLCryoV		1	1	5	5	1				13
HP	2-mL-cryotube		1	1	5	5	1				13
SG	5-mL-cryotube		2	2	10	10	2				26
FC	2-mL-cryotube		3	3	15	15	3				39
HC	2-mL-cryotube		3	3	15	15	3				39
SEM	petri-slide		1	1	5	5	1				13
FM20	50-mL-falcon			1	2	2	1				6
3DEM20	50 mL falcon										0
E20	15-mL-falcon		1	1	2	2	1				7
S20	5-mL-cryotube		1	1	2	2	1				7
S20-L	5-mL-falcon		1	1	2	2	1				7
PM-HG20	Zip-lock		1	1	2	2	1				7
MB20	4-mL-Vial		1	1	2	2	1				7
CP50	petri-slide		1	1	2	2	1				7
SCP50	petri-slide										0
F200	250-mL-bottle		1	1	2	2	1				7
E200	15-mL-falcon		1	1	2	2	1				7
S200	5-mL-cryotube		1	1	2	2	1				7
S200-L	5-mL-falcon		1	1	2	2	1				7
PM-HG200	Zip-lock		1	1	2	2	1				7
MB200	4-mL-Vial		1	1	2	2	1				7
CP200	petri-slide										0
F680	250-mL-bottle										0
F2000	250-mL-bottle										0
E2000	15-mL-falcon										0
E680	15-mL-falcon										0
S680-L	MULTIPLATES										0
SP330	2-mL-cryotube				2	1	9				12
MP330	2-mL-cryotube										0
CP330	petri-slide		1	1	1	1	1				5
S025-L	15-mL-falcon		1	1	5	5	1				13
S520-L	5-mL-falcon		1	1	5	5	1				13
FMS	5-mL-falcon		2	2	10	10	2				26
3DEM5	5-mL-Cryotube										0
E5	15ml falcon										0
SEM5	petrislide										0
AI	petri-slide		24							1	25
AS	2-mL-cryotube		24							1	25
AF	Zip-lock		24							1	25
TOC	30-mL-bottle										0
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube										0
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube										0
	TOTAL	0	126	58	201	200	66	0	0	17	668